

ISSUES OF LANGUAGE AND STYLE IN AUDIOVISUAL JOURNALISM

Khazratova Kunduz Mamaraimovna

Senior English teacher of the Uzbekistan State
World Languages University, Uzbekistan,

E-mail: kunduz.khazratova@gmail.com

Abstract: This paper aims to explore importance of audiovisual tools in modern curriculum. Today's world is visually oriented world, a world of virtual information technology and opportunities. It actively used for cognitive purposes in all spheres of human activity, including journalism education.

Key words: language in media, audiovisual methodology, learning styles, role of audio visual technology, effective audio visual aids, audio visual skills.

Аннотация: Цель данной статьи - изучить важность аудиовизуальных инструментов в современной учебной программе. Сегодняшний мир - это визуально ориентированный мир, мир виртуальных информационных технологий и возможностей. Он активно используется в познавательных целях во всех сферах человеческой деятельности, включая журналистское образование.

Ключевые слова: язык в медиа, аудиовизуальная методология, стили обучения, роль аудиовизуальных технологий, эффективные аудиовизуальные средства, аудиовизуальные навыки.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning maqsadi zamonaviy o'quv dasturida audiovizual vositalarning ahamiyatini o'rganishdir. Bugungi dunyo-bu vizual yo'naltirilgan dunyo, virtual axborot texnologiyalari va imkoniyatlari dunyosi. U inson faoliyatining barcha sohalarida, shu jumladan jurnalistik ta'limda kognitiv maqsadlarda faol qo'llaniladi.

Kalit so'zlar: ommaviy axborot vositalaridagi til, audiovizual metodologiya, o'qitish uslublari, audiovizual texnologiyalarning roli, samarali audiovizual vositalar, audiovizual ko'nikmalar.

Nowadays modern students are a generation fully brought up under the influence of information technology. The globalization era, the rapid development of the media has changed the didactic landscape. The role of language in the media whether in English language or some other languages that is generally understood by the originator and the receiver, people use language to exchange information and shape the views of others in the mass media. Language and media ideologies intertwine in complex ways. People's ideas about different communicative media and different media functions shape the ways they use these media, similar to how language ideologies impact the way people speak.

The language is very important in journalism. Your main task as a journalist is to help people understand what is happening around them; in their village, in their country and in the world. Most readers or listeners will not have your knowledge of language, so you must simplify it for them. Media are dominating presenters of language in our society at large. News is determined by values and the kind of language in which that news is told, reflects and expresses these values. The readers feel that the way in which language is used, must affect the content of what we receive from media.

There are different types of media languages which include written, verbal, non-verbal, visual and aural. The main principle of language is we communicate with each other to express our thoughts, feelings, ideas and emotions with the help of language. Language is a social, cultural and geographical phenomenon. Man acquires language skills when one is exposed to real situations in the society. Some elements of media language are colour, composition, editing style, narrative structure, sound design - but there are always more elements to look at and understand. Language is an aspect of our culture which is not an exception to the media's influence. Just like other aspects of our culture, the media has the power to both influence a societies' language use as well as reflect a societies' language use. Audio-visual media is effective for learning. One of classroom learning success parameter is the use of appropriate learning media, which include audio visual media. Interactive and varied audio visual media can be used to stimulate student to think critically and actively. Language and media ideologies intertwine in complex ways. People's ideas about different communicative media and different media functions shape the ways they use these media, similar to how language ideologies impact the way people speak. One of classroom learning success parameter is the use of appropriate learning media, which include audio visual media. Interactive and varied audio visual media can be used to stimulate student to think critically and actively.

What is the role of audio-visual method in language teaching? - The goal of audio-visual aids is to enhance teacher's ability to present the lesson in simple, effective and easy to understand for the students. Audiovisual materials make learning more permanent since students use more than one sense. The concept of audiovisual aids is not new. Mayer (2001) defines multimedia as the combination of various digital media types, such as text, video and sound into an integrated multi-

sensory interactive presentation to convey a message to an audience. It provides students with a medium for communication and offers them new insights into organizing and evaluating information. Reddy (2008:26) states that “audiovisual education consists of the uses of interactional devices such as films projectors, radio, charts, models. etc”

Besides that, scientist Reddy (2008: 27-28) states that there are some advantages of audiovisual aids: the students become more active due to involvement of more than one sense organ, the student's attention becomes intensive, students can be more motivated, it provides students with opportunities to handle and manipulate certain things and articles.

Therefore, in order to maximize the quality of students' knowledge, to their interest and increase their personal competencies. It is a good plan to combine interactive learning with the use of audiovisual tools.

Audio-visual (AV) learning is a type of learning which is described by delivery and the use of instructional content that involves sound (auditory stimuli) and sight (visual stimuli). The term “learning style” is one that's commonly used in education. This popular theory teaches that people learn better when taught in a way that matches their learning style—whether that's auditory, tactile, visual, or kinesthetic. The 4 main styles of learning, perhaps the most simple way of describing 'learning styles' is to say that they are different methods of learning or understanding new information, the way a person takes in, understands, expresses and remembers information. There are 4 predominant learning styles: Visual, Auditory, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic. The benefits of audio-visual is that audio visual technology allows teachers to present information in a way that is more visually appealing and memorable for students. Furthermore, incorporating audio visual technology into classroom learning encourages active participation and engagement from all students. Audio visual communication is a productive form of communication. Using sound and lighting equipment improves communication by heightening the awareness of your audience's sight and hearing. Audiences who use more of their senses to engage at events remember those events for a longer period of time. Audio-visual materials are used effectively in communication. Audio-Visual aids such as interactive boards can be used during the lecture, to make the presentation more interesting. Using audio-visuals can improve the visual and auditory perception of students. The teacher

can easily show the class her note and then ask them to discuss it. One of the forms of media that can be used in teaching English is video. The use of AVM in the classroom can guide the study activities in an interesting way. AVM provide information to both eyes and ears, so students can see communication in action and it presents language in a lively way. For many journalists today, English is the primary language used for news reporting on radio, television, online, and in print. If you're an aspiring journalist you'll be expected to have a firm grasp of the English language and its grammar rule. How many languages should a journalist know? David Brewer, British media strategy consultant who founded “Media Helping Media” says, that “to be an international journalist, do a languages degree – Mandarin, Arabic, Spanish, Russian, Swahili, French all cover a big chunk of the world. Ideally do a joint degree with two languages”.

Formal, concise language with short sentences, rather than descriptive narrative writing. Third person and past tense, although note that the final paragraph may switch to future tense. Direct speech using the reporting verb, such as 'said', rather than 'fiction-sounding' verbs such as 'whispered', or 'cried'.

The learning styles are important. Learning styles are the various ways in which people learn and process information. They can impact how your learners understand, retain, and apply new knowledge. That's why understanding their learning styles can help improve the learning process and ultimately lead to better performance.

Some of the key skills required to become an audio visual technician include: Technical proficiency: Audio visual technicians must be proficient in the use of audio and visual equipment. This includes understanding how to set up and operate equipment, as well as troubleshooting technical issues.

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Audio-visual aids are important tools for easy and effective teaching learning process which retain the concepts better and for longer duration. It develops the reflective and analytical thinking of students and teachers and improves the whole teaching learning environment.

The advantage of audio visual in communication. It is the combination of sight and sound that promotes and reinforces this retention, and enables an audience to better connect to the brand or message. AV makes it easier for your audience to psychologically access and remember information once they have left the event. AV can also save your business time!

The disadvantages of audiovisual learning. Limited transferability: Audio-visual aids may not be as effective at helping students transfer knowledge to new situations or contexts, as they often rely on a specific set of stimuli and may not encourage critical thinking or problem-solving skills. The benefits of audio visual systems are using audiovisual (AV) technology for businesses can have several advantages, such as improved communication, enhanced presentations, increased collaboration, better customer experience, cost savings, brand promotion, event management and emergency response. Visual learners can remember 75% of what they see or read, so they take lots of notes. They have a good sense of direction because they can read maps. Their love of balance means they tend to be neat. They often do well in class tests because they remember where the information is and can see it written down. The visual learners process the information best if they can see it. The auditory learners like to hear information. The read-write learners prefer to see the written words. The kinaesthetic learners like to acquire information through experience and practice. Electronic media consisting of and/or possessing both visual component and sound. Examples of audiovisual media include films (movies), television, video games, slideshows, etc. The first chapter serves as an introduction to international political communication and associated terms. The audiovisual method refers to both sound and pictures which is typically in the form of slides or video and recorded speech or music; all is visual presentations that are shown by the teacher to the students. Audio visual materials are instructional aids, devices and materials which provide multi- sensory experiences in the teaching- learning process. These materials translate the most difficult, hard to see and understand abstract concepts into concrete realities and experience. Visual resources include photographs, film, video, paintings, drawings, cartoons, prints, designs, and three-dimensional art such as sculpture and architecture and can be categorized as fine art or documentary record.

Characteristics of Good Audio-Visual Aids (Teaching aids)

- They should be meaningful and purposeful.
- They should be accurate in every respect.
- They should be simple.
- They should be cheap.
- As for as possible, they should be improvised.
- They should be large enough to be properly seen by the students for whom they are meant. There are various types of audiovisual materials ranging from filmstrips, microforms, slides, projected opaque materials, tape recording, and flashcards.

Conclusion

Interactive technologies allow for interactive learning modes with direct application of interactive learning technologies. The interactive whiteboard software gives to user access to an extensive database digital images, educational content, as well as same wide range of modern tool. In conclusion, the use active of modern information and technical means of audiovisual level today in the educational process seems to be indisputable.

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